

Video Shot Boundary Detection using Machine Learning and Confirmation Stage

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Abstract - Shot Boundary Detection or Temporal Video Segmentation is the building block for various video processing application like Video Summarizing, Video Classification, Content-based Video Indexing and Retrieval and many more. So, it becomes crucial to construct a robust Shot Boundary Detection procedure for efficient implementation of video processing systems. In this paper, an efficient dual stage approach to a shot boundary detection procedure has been proposed, which eventually outperforms various contemporary Shot Boundary Detection approaches. firstly, possible transition frames are detected by training a Feed-Forward Neural Network, whose weights and biases are stochastically optimized by a hybridized Grey-Wolf-Optimization and Cuckoo-Search algorithm. This process mainly works with the fusion of supervised learning (labelled data) and Reinforcement Learning (Exploration and Exploitation). This results, possible abrupt transition frames generated by this methodology. These frames are further pruned with other features including illumination features to increase the accuracy of the Shot Boundary Detection in terms of precision and F1 Score.

Keywords – Cuckoo Search, Content Based Video Indexing, Feed-Forward Neural Network, Grey-Wolf-Optimization, Exploration, Exploitation, Reinforcement Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern era, videos play an essential role in information exchange, which also can be used for various application for the proper transportation of words with action. Managing the entire video data and analysing its meanings become difficult. Also, it causes an increase in the transmission volume and repository size. Moreover, like in earlier days accessing and indexing the video data using video name has become obsolete [1]. Human minds are trained to analyse the pictorial data faster than the text, making it easier for a human to work with the video data. But it becomes an overhead to manage the video data for various reasons like bulky information, huge repository size and so on. Hence, to operate the video for the analysis and indexing, the video needs to be fragmented into meaningful units called shots. Shot Boundary Detection is a part of Video Segmentation. It is also called as Temporal Video Segmentation. The other part of Video Segmentation is also called as Semantic Video Segmentation. In our work we will mainly focus on Temporal Video Segmentation or Shot Boundary Detection [2].

Shot Boundary Detection can be used in the post processing of the videos. For example, an application may choose a particular picture from each shot and pacify the following queries “Show me all the films where there is a dog in it” For this type of application, the Shot Boundary Detection or detection of the transition frames becomes very important [3].

A. Applications of Machine Learning

In modern era, there are numerous types of Neural Network that exists in the literature, i.e. Feed-Forward Neural Network, Kohonen's Self Organizing Maps, Recurrent Neural Network, Spiking Neural Network. Learning methodologies as per training data in these networks can be widely segmented into three categories viz, Supervised Learning and Unsupervised Learning and Semi supervised Learning. Generally, in Supervised Learning, the networks are enriched with Feedbacks externally (Supervisor or labelled data). Whereas in case of Unsupervised Learning supervisor adapt themselves without any external support [4]. There exist two types of learning methodologies by means of the process of learning in literature, viz, Deterministic and Stochastic. Deterministic Learning methodology can be further categorised into two types, back-propagation and gradient based methods. In deterministic learning, the system generates same output if the input samples remain consistent. The advantage of using deterministic learning methodology is, it gets simplified mathematical deduction in case of finding the output, it has a quick solution than a stochastic optimization technique. But it suffers from local optima entrapment problem (Assuming the local optima as the global optima solution), However in contrast to that, stochastic method uses stochastic optimization techniques to minimize the error and maximize the performance of the system. Stochastic optimization techniques start from a random solution, from a solution space and then gradually it evolves to the actual solution. Random nature is the essential component that applies to the initial solution and then method of improving the solution. So, in our project we have used stochastic learning algorithm to avoid local optima problem and for more consistency in results.

B. What is a Video? Inception to the video processing

A video is nothing but a series of images which changes sequentially to create an illusion of moving objects. So, a video can be illustrated as a sequence of images that moves in a temporal manner. Generally, an image can be thought as a visual representation of something that we perceive. Image can be represented as a two-dimensional matrix. Hence in our further studies, we shall evaluate upon computing images called frame. So,

Fig 1: Video: A sequence of frames

working with videos are basically working with image. Because the processing of a video gradually comes down into processing of images called frame.

C. Types of Transitions

Different types from one shot to another can be found in a video [5]. The main two types of transitions can be found in a video. One is soft transition and another is hard transition. To build an accurate hard transition has been done in our work. Whereas soft transition or gradual transitions are mainly of three types 1) Fade 2) Dissolve and 3) wipe.

For example, figure below describes how a Cut or abrupt transition takes place. In the figure below we can clearly see that at what position or boundary shot is terminated or when a shot is started afterwards. We have to detect that position in our work.

Fig 2: The concept of Transition frame

The increase in the expansion of multimedia technologies lead to drastic usage of video data. This increment in video usage has urged the requirement of technology and tools that can help in effective video automatic annotation, classification, indexing, retrieval and summarization, in order to apply all these technologies is video shot boundary detection or temporal video segmentation. The exactness of the subsequent processes of these approaches depends on the correctness of the shot boundary Detection process. Although there are so many methodologies have been proposed for the purpose. But there is a lack of proper methodologies that can withstand with the challenges faced by the researchers as well as users. In our work we have given a robust illumination invariant solution that solves the problems given below.

1. Pixel based approach solutions are highly sensitive to object and camera motion
2. Histogram based approaches also have camera motion problem, especially in pan and zoom.
3. Most of the solutions are sensitive to flash light, similar background and monochrome frames.
4. Motion based approaches are computationally tedious to compute the motion vector related computation.
5. Dim lighting frames also creates problems in shot boundary detection.
6. Calculation of threshold values as it differs from one video to another video.

The main objectives of our work are:

1. Developing and approach to tackle the problem of object motion and lightning effect effectively.
2. To develop an automatic and adaptive threshold calculation for classifying transitions.
3. To develop a machine learning based approach so that non transition regions are effectively eliminated, which will reduce the computation time of the system.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various methods of shot boundary detection have been proposed in the existing literature of the video segmentation. The entire shot boundary detection procedure can be subdivided into three modules.

- A. *Feature of visual content:* Here information is extracted from the video frame and this is called as representation of Visual Information.
- B. *Construction of the similarity or dissimilarity matrices:* This is the intermediate stage between representation of visual information and classification of similarity and dissimilarity signals. In this step the feature difference of two consecutive frames is computed.
- C. *Classification of continuity matrices:* In this module, the actual segmentation of the video frames is done. The transition frames (Hard and Soft) are detected and shot boundary detection can be executed.

There are several approaches by which we can determine the previous work done in this topic [6].

There are several methodologies have been proposed in the literature for shot boundary detection. Some of the papers are chosen and merits and demerits of work done by the previous researchers are discussed below.

D. Discussion for the work done in this area:

There is a robust shot boundary detection procedure using local and global feature exists in the literature. Entropy is used as the global feature, and SURF (Speeded Up Robust Features) are used as local features. The combination of those two constructs a great tool by which the false alarms created by sudden illumination change can be easily identified. The computation time has been saved considerably as each and every frame of the video has not been considered in this process. The key frames are pruned first and then the computation has been performed [7]. As there are several advantages of the paper it suffers from several drawbacks like the designing of the threshold value has not properly done and it creates an ambiguity for threshold calculation. Various types of contemporary methodologies have been proposed in past for Shot Boundary Detection. Some of these methodologies is discussed below.

A great work done in the domain of local features [8]. Here we can understand the computation of feature vectors which is computed from several frames, not computing each and every frame feature vector. It also highlights how proper implementation of extracting SURF (Speeded Up Robust Feature) which is a local feature, can also have greater accuracy in terms of Recall 0.9984 and precision of 0.977. It also not sensitive to motion effects and sudden camera movements. Here also the problem of threshold calculation of videos remains an open area of research.

A colour histogram based approach has been proposed in this paper [9]. The difference involving RGB components, A well-defined implementation of a mean block of a frame is given in this paper which involves a great problem-solving capability in case of gradual transition detection. The abrupt transitions can be easily identified as it involves spike in the plotting of the histogram.

The genetic algorithm based approach as discussed in paper [2]. It takes previously observed datasets of various contemporary shot boundary detection algorithms and produces a good result in terms of F1 Score. A fusion of fuzzy approach to feature space and genetic algorithm mutation gives a robust result in detection of transition frames. A well-defined classification in the membership function is provided at the first time to classify the output frames.

In this paper dual stage implementation of the shot detection has been proposed in the case of transition detection which provides a robust approach for the removal of false positive in the shot boundaries [10]. Here the overall computation of feature extraction from all the frames has been reduced due to computation of possible transition frames by applying feed-forward neural network. The edge weights are optimized by the fusion of Particle Swarm Optimization and Gravitational Search Algorithm. The features like (Colour Histogram Difference, CIEDE 2000 Colour Difference and Normalized 3D Euclidean Standard Deviation) is computed from the frames and given as an input to the Feed-Forward Neural Network.

The paper comprises with basic terminologies and concepts of video and video segmentation techniques that creates a robust foundation for any video segmentation work [11]. It gives detail explanation about the dataset and corresponding to its output. So, a well-organized knowledge of various contemporary methodologies can be found.

With the advent of Hadoop, it is easier to deal with large video data. This paper mainly objectifies the preprocessing of the video frames using background subtraction algorithms [12]. A Map-Reduced based background subtraction algorithm which renders well accuracy, efficiency, and scalability in video processing. This paper proposes single frame oriented and frame series-oriented processing. Although this paper proposes a better approach than the other contemporary approaches. But it doesn't give full roadmap towards implementation of the work.

In this era of machine learning there is a need of comparison between contemporary methods like K-Means, Region-Growing, Mean-Shift and watershed algorithm. The performance analysis is performed by the following quality metric parameters such as 1) Grey Level Energy 2) Discrete Entropy 3) Normalized Mutual Information 4) Information Redundancy and 5) Mean Square Error. The above mentioned approaches with modified methodologies has also been explained in this paper which includes segmentation of various types of videos like sports videos [13].

This paper provides a comprehensive review in the area of shot boundary detection covering almost all the approaches available with its mathematical explanations. It gives a blueprint to extract the local and global feature extraction. The comprehensive study has been done by comparing the state-of-the-art method [14].

The gradient similarity and CIEDE2000 colour difference can be used to detect the transition robust to sudden illumination change. And most importantly the concept of Adaptive Threshold is also introduced to find a generic threshold calculation in all approaches. Smoothing of luminance values and continuity matrix calculation is done to detect the actual transition frames. Here also possible transition frames are firstly detected by the extracted features and the algorithm is applied to find the true cut and gradual frames. In this work involving computation of CIEDE 2000 colour difference for detecting abrupt transition and luminance pattern for the gradual transition maintaining overall accuracy of 92.01%. The CIEDE 2000 has the capability of mapping all the colours which are recognizable in human eye. Experimental results are further matched and verified with TREC Vid 2001 and TREC Vid 2007 databases with numerous various types of video collection. Pattern matching is used for detection of gradual transition [15].

This is the approach in which we can find how the combinations of various shot boundary detection algorithms can be used. This paper also comprises with the usage of Weka 3.0 as a software for the implementation of the combinations of algorithms [6]. The main foundation of our optimization technique is this paper is the grey wolf optimization, which is a stochastic optimization technique in which the problem of local optima entrapment can easily be avoided. This algorithm has the great convergence rate compared to other optimization techniques. A comparative study of various optimization algorithms with various datasets has also been done in this approach [16].

This metaheuristic approach to the shot boundary detection gives a new pathway to the stochastic optimization techniques which will be discussed in this paper. This also provides a basis for comparison of various multimodal and multivariate functions. The usefulness of Grey-Wolf Optimization and its greater convergence rate can be easily comprehended in this paper [17].

By detailed analysis of the research work done in this area we can come into conclusion that various approaches are there in shot boundary detection procedure. Such as

A. Pixel Based Approach

Frame difference of every pixel can be computed in this approach. The concept of adaptive threshold is first introduced in this approach. The subdomain of pixel-based approach, the block-based approaches are also called as macroblocks, which is based on pixel comparison. In the concept of macroblocks each frame is broken into three types of macroblocks, I type, P type and B type. I macroblocks are coded in different manner from other macroblocks, and used when the segment is very different from the other segment parts used. P macroblocks are predictable macroblocks, B macroblocks are bidirectional macroblocks.

B. Feature Based Approach

In this approach we extract the feature from the video frames. Features can be classified into two types.

A. *Global Features* Texture, Colour, Shape, Edge, Text are computed and compared with subsequent frame in this approach. Global features are used as a technique to represent the whole content of the video frame. The global features requires less amount of memory and less calculation [7].

B. *Local Features* Local Features are the feature vectors to show the point of interest of the video frames. The process of local features is mainly classified into two ways a) Feature detection and 2) Feature description. Local Feature detection is here to detect a set of key points and regions of interest. Whereas feature description is used to extract stable features from the key points. The examples of commonly used local features are SIFT (Scale invariant feature transform), SURF (Speeded-Up Robust Feature), MSER (maximally stable external region) [8].

A part from those approaches there are several approaches like Edge Based, Model Based, Clustering Based, Histogram Based, Luminance Based, Statistical Difference Based approaches are widely used in this domain.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The entire system is implemented in two parts. The first part is the possible abrupt transition detection part and the subsequent part is the confirmation part or final abrupt transition detection part. The proposed system is depicted by the block diagram as shown in figure 3.

Fig 3: Block diagram of Entire Work

At the first stage a feed-forward neural network or multi-layer perceptron for training the system is used. The system is trained with the dataset constructed by the absolute difference of the Grey-Level-

Cooccurrence Matrix (GLCM) features are extracted from each of the frame of the video. The GLCM construction is shown in the figure 4. The GLCM is constructed by considering two adjacent pixels of a single image. When two pixels co-occur with angular value 0-degree, corresponding GLCM will have entry in the matrix to be constructed. We can also consider various angular co-occurrence values. The computation with various degrees is shown in figure 5.

A. Feature Extraction

As the implementation of the system has been done, the feature extraction is also done using two phases, in the first part the features are extracted for the training phase of the system, as in this project we are mainly considered with GLCM features. Which is mainly considered with the texture of the image. Texture gives an information about special arrangement of colours or image textures are complex visual patterns composed of property or area. Texture of a point is undefined. So, second order statistical features are constructed by GLCM. Which contains more information than 1D histogram.

Fig 4: Construction of Grey Level Co-occurrence Matrix

An image is composed of pixels with an intensity (A specific grey Level), The GLCM IS tabulate of how often different combination of Grey Level co-occur in an image or image section. It can also be referred to as cooccurrence distribution. Texture feature calculation use the contents of the GLCM to give the measure of the variation in the intensity at the point of interest. The GLCM measures can be calculated by computation of any other degree other than 0 degree. The computation of GLCM by various degree is shown below.

Fig: 5 GLCM construction in Various degrees

From the GLCM several features are extracted from the image frames like contrast, correlation, Homogeneity, Energy.

A. Contrast

It is the spatial frequency of an image. The contrast can be expressed as the difference between the highest and lowest values of the contiguous set of pixels. It specifies the of local variations present in the image frame. Linear patterns in an image can be found by the GLCM contrast measure. Contrast is 0 for a constant image. Contrast (C_i) can be explained using Eq. 4.1. where $P_{i,j}$ is the second order probability of cooccurring the pixels i and j . The contrast (C_i) can be defined as -

$$\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} P_{i,j} |i - j|^2 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

B. Correlation

Correlation measure provides the measure of how correlated a pixel is to its neighbour over the whole image. It ranges over the values -1 to 1. Correlation of constant image is undefined. Correlation (Co_i) can be evaluated using Eq.2. Where μ is the mean and σ is the variance measure of the pixels. Correlation (Co_i) can be defined as

$$\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} P_{i,j} \left| \frac{(i - \mu_i)(j - \mu_j)}{\sqrt{(\sigma_i^2)(\sigma_j^2)}} \right| \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

C. Homogeneity

Homogeneity is also called inverse difference moment. It has maximum value when all the elements of the image frame are similar. It is more sensitive to the presence of near diagonal elements of the GLCM. Homogeneity increases if contrast decreases while energy is kept constant. Homogeneity (H_i) can be expressed by Eq. 3.

$$\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} \frac{P_{i,j}}{1 + |i - j|} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

D. Energy

Energy measures uniformity of pixels in the image frame which represents pixel pair repetition known as textural uniformity. It can detect disorders in the textures. The maximum value of energy can reach to one. Entropy is strongly but inversely proportional to Energy. Energy(E_i) measure can be evaluated using Eq. 4

$$\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} P_{ij}^2 \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

B. The Training of Feed-Forward Neural Network

The Grey-Wolf-Optimization has capability of optimizing multivariate function. In our work, we are minimizing the hypothetical function which gives output as Mean-Square-Error and takes input as the extracted GLCM features. The weights and biases are the variables of the hypothetical function. The stochastic learning approach in by considering those variables can be applied in our problem.

At first the Cut transitions are detected manually by taking some of the videos of TRECVID 2001 and 2007 [18]. After that the training data-set is constructed.

The training of any neural network is the most important component in any machine learning system. In this system we are using supervised learning which considers the feedback from an external source or labelled data. The data-set is constructed by labelling the transition and non-transition frames manually.

The training phase is started by training the Neural Network by repeated epochs. Experimentally the value of epochs is taken as 250 as it gives the optimal results.

Stochastic algorithm like hybridized Grey-Wolf Optimization with Cuckoo- Search is used as it is free from local optima entrapment, All the swarm-intelligence based algorithms are dependent upon two basic operations, namely, exploration and exploitation. The efficiency of swarm-intelligence based meta-heuristic algorithms lies in the balance between exploration and exploitation. Grey-Wolf optimizer has an inbuilt capability of balancing exploration and exploitation [17]. The architecture of the neural network is chosen as 4-9-1, 4 input neurons as 4 types of GLCM features have been extracted. 9 hidden neurons have been considered. Because experimentally it has been seen that optimal number of hidden neurons = $2 \times N + 1$

Figure 6: Architecture of the neural Network

A. Construction of Training Data

The GLCM features are extracted from all the frames of the video. 300 different entries are constructed by feature difference between consecutive frames of abrupt transitions. And 300 other non-transition feature

difference are recorded. All the transition and non-transition frames are chosen in a pure randomized manner in an unbiased way (consecutive transition or non-transition frames are avoided). Thus, a training data consisting of 600 entries are constructed.

At the second or confirmation stage we apply further computation in the output of possible transition frames which we get from the multi-layer-perceptron (MLP).

B. Feature Extraction in the confirmation stage

After getting the possible transitions from the first stage, it is important to prune the extraneous transition in order to improve the system in terms of precision. So, from the possible transitions further features are extracted. We have taken three features in the confirmation stage. Those are 1) Local Binary Pattern 2) 3D standard deviation 3) 3D pixel difference

A. 3D Standard Deviation Feature:

In this feature from the pixel difference from the mean is calculated from each plane of i^{th} and $i+1^{th}$ frame. In

$$SD_i = \frac{\sqrt{(\phi_R^i - \phi_R^{i+1})^2 + (\phi_G^i - \phi_G^{i+1})^2 + (\phi_B^i - \phi_B^{i+1})^2}}{P \times Q} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where ,

$$\phi = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^n (x_i - \mu)^2}$$

μ ' is the mean and of the 'x_i' pixel.

B. 3D pixel difference feature

The pixel difference between the consecutive frames is calculated, and the three colour components of a frame is computed further, at last the pixel difference of the consecutive frames are calculated.

$$PD_i = \sqrt{\sum(\sum(\delta_R^i - \delta_R^{i+1})^2 + \sum(\delta_G^i - \delta_G^{i+1})^2 + \sum(\delta_B^i - \delta_B^{i+1})^2)} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Where δ = pixel difference of the consecutive frames.

C. LBP Standard Deviation Feature:

To derive the local textural patterns of an image, LBP can be used as an illumination invariant feature of an image, this is due to blocking of the image is done instead of computation in the entire image. In our experiment the default block size is taken as 3 X 3.

The calculation is shown in the figure.

$$LBP = \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} s(n_i - G_c)2^i s(x) \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

The value of the equation becomes 1 if the value of 'x' is > 0 , and it becomes 0 otherwise.

C. Reason for using Hybrid Grey-Wolf -Optimization

Grey-Wolf-Optimization (GWO) is multi-solution based meta-heuristic algorithm that often gives better convergence than the popular meta-heuristic algorithms like, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). Due to its rapid convergence GWO can suffer from bad local searching in some cases, to resolve that issue Cuckoo Search (CS) algorithm is integrated with GWO, as a result we transfer the control to CS algorithm in identifying the position of the Grey-Wolf. The concept of levy fights gives more accuracy in terms of local searching in the hybridized GWO algorithm. GWO gives high classification accuracy whenever we apply it for classification problem. The problem of evolutionary strategies and other introductory swarm-based algorithms in the case of optimization problem is imbalance between exploration and exploitation, which is taken care on GWO.

IV. ALGORITHMS

The main pseudocode of the system is shown below. The GWO + Cuckoo Search portion is separated as algorithm 2.

Algorithm-1: Main pseudocode of the system

input	Video, V
Output	Abrupt transition frames`
Procedure	GWO + CS algorithm (I, key)
1.	V ← Read Videoframes
2.	Calculate GLCM for the frames
3.	Contrast1 ← GLCM1.Contrast
4.	Correlation1 ← GLCM1.Correlation
5.	Homogeinity1 ← GLCM1.Homogeinity
6.	Energy1 ← GLCM1.Energy
7.	[C, C', H, E] ← [Contrast, Correlation, Homogeinity, Energy]
8.	F ← Creation of the continuity matrix -----1(Shown in algorithm 2)
9.	Training by GWO + CS----- (Shown in algorithm 2)
10.	NOF = Number of frames of the video
11.	for i = 2 to NOF do
12.	[C, C', E, H] = GLCM _i
13.	[C, C', E, H] _i = [C, C', E, H] _i - [C, C', E, H] _{i-1}
14.	C ← Possible Transition Frames for GWO+CS
15.	LBP ← C.LBP ----- (Feature extraction for confirmation stage)
16.	St ← C.St----- (Feature extraction for confirmation stage)
17.	P ← C.P----- (Feature extraction for confirmation stage)
18.	th1&th2&th3 ← Experimental Thresholds---- (LBP, St and P)
19.	if LBP(i + 1) < th1 & LBP(i - 1) < th1 & LBP(i) < th1 then
20.	CC(i) ← C(i)
21.	end if or
22.	if St(i + 1) < th2 & St(i - 1) < th2 & St(i) < th2 then
23.	CC(i) ← C(i)
24.	end if or
25.	if P(i + 1) < th2 & P(i - 1) < th2 & P(i) < th2 then
26.	CC(i) ← C(i)
27.	end if
28.	CC----- (Abrupt transition frames)

Algorithm – 2: Pseudo-code of GWO + CS

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Input: [C,C',E,H](Transition from extracted features)
Output: GWO+CS Algorithm (C, C', E, H)
1. Collect GLCM feature difference from the abrupt transition
2. Create continuity matrix from the collected features collected from transitions.
3. Initialize Parameters: Population size, Maximize Iteration Range
4. Solution Space: ← Find the weights and biases of the multilayer perceptron, Find the best(F $\alpha$ ), 2nd best(F $\beta$ ), 3rd best (F $\gamma$ ) solutions,
5. for i = 1 to maximum iterations do
6.     Compute Random parameters ( $\alpha, \beta, \gamma$ )
7.     And so X1, X2, X3
8.     Check the bounds
9.     Performed greedy selection
10.    if current solution is better than the previous solution then
11.        Solution( $\alpha$ score) ← Current Solution
12.    end if
13.     $\alpha$ positions ← CuckooSearch(Current positions)
14.    Select the transition for the best solution obtained by hybridized GWO
        C(i) = corresponding transitions
15. end for
16. C------(Possible Abrupt Transition Frames)
    
```

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We first analyze the convergence of optimization algorithms in the training datasets, in many cases it has been observed that hybridized GWO outperforms GWO in terms of mean-square-error and convergence of predicted outcome and target.

Here we have used TRECVID 2001 and TRECVID 2007 videos for computation of cut transitions and further computed into accuracy measures (Precision, Recall, and F1 Score) as per the output of the MLP. Some of the accuracy metrics are shown in the table below. **True positives (TP)** denotes that the count of the detected positive transitions corresponding to actual positive Transitions. **False Positive, (FP)** is when the predicted output is positive, but actually it is not. **False Negative (the miss transitions)**. Higher the number of **False positive**, lesser the value of **precision**. Higher the number of **False Negative**, lesser the number of **Recall**

So experimentally,

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \dots\dots\dots(5.1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \dots\dots\dots (5.2)$$

$$F1 \text{ Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Table 1 Accuracy measures without confirmation stage.

Video Name	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Total Cuts	Misses
anni002	0.116	1.0	0.2075	12	0
anni003	0.0377	1.0	0.0726	24	0
anni004	0.0149	0.923	0.029	13	2
anni007	0.079	1.0	0.146	5	0
BOR03	0.025	0.988	0.024	334	4
NAD57	0.0203	0.933	0.0397	45	3
indi001	0.110	1.0	0.198	11	0
BG-16336	0.066	0.90	0.124	20	2
BG-3314	0.0039	0.91	0.0074	12	1
BG-3097	0.0267	0.9565	0.0996	23	2

Table 2 Accuracy measures which is computed from selected TREC Vid 2001 and 2007 video data with confirmation stage.

Video Name	Experimental Thresholds			Precision	Recall	F1 Score
	STD	ED	LBP			
BG_16336	0.06	0.72	1	0.947	0.947	0.947
BG_3314	0.03	0.59	1	0.9166	0.9166	0.9166
BG_3097	0.55	1	1	1	0.913	0.954
anni007	0.2	1	1	1	1	1
anni002	0.077	0.72	1	1	0.916	0.956
anni003	0.16	0.51	1	0.82	0.96	0.884
anni004	0.053	1	1	0.846	0.916	0.956
NAD57	0.0685	1	1	0.907	0.928	0.917
indi001	0.13	0.8	1	0.933	0.933	0.933
BOR03	0.08	1	0.815	0.0833	0.911	0.87

For all the videos the computation time has been tracked and recorded. In every problem there will be a trade-off between computation time and accuracy. In the table a visualization can be done of the tradeoffs.

Table 3 shows the computation time of the system with respect to every run of the videos.

Video name	Total Frames	Computation Time(s)	F1 Score
anni002	2294	1100	0.956
anni003	4267	756	0.884
anni004	3895	2350	0.88
anni007	1590	700	1
BOR03	48450	8400	0.87

NAD57	12510	3569	0.917
indi001	1687	965	0.933
BG_16336	2466	170	0.947
BG_3314	35802	3186	0.9166
BG_3097	44991	1452	0.954
Average F1 Score			0.926

A. Adaptive Threshold Calculation

From table 4.2 we can observe that the threshold value has been calculated from the given equations. Th1 dynamically sets the threshold value for Feature 3D Euclidean Distance.

Similarly Th2 Dynamically sets the value of the threshold of the feature 3D Pixel Difference.

Similarly Th3 Dynamically sets the value of the threshold of the feature LBP.

Mathematically we can write as

$$\text{Th1} = C_1^1 \mu + C_2^1 \sigma + C_3^1 \delta$$

$$\text{Th2} = C_1^2 \mu + C_2^2 \sigma + C_3^2 \delta$$

$$\text{Th3} = C_1^3 \mu + C_2^3 \sigma + C_3^3 \delta$$

Where μ = mean of the feature, σ is the standard deviation of the feature,

Similarly Th3 Dynamically sets the value of the threshold of the feature LBP, δ is the median value of the corresponding feature.

And the values of C1, C2, C3 can be given as $C_1^1 = 7$, $C_2^1 = 0.3$, $C_3^1 = 2.5$, $C_1^2 = 3.2$, $C_2^2 = 0.75$, $C_3^2 = 0.75$, $C_1^3 = 3.5$, $C_2^3 = 0.85$, $C_3^3 = 5.89$, All the values of the constants are set experimentally to make the threshold adaptive.

B. SComparison with other State-of-the-Art methods

The comparison with the proposed system and other state of the art methodologies has been done to conclude and benchmark the systems performance. Mainly the comparison has been done with respect of F1 Score and computation time.

Table 4 shows the Comparison of F1 score with other state of the art techniques

Method Name	F1 Score
Deep Structured Model tang <i>et al.</i> [1]	0.91
Multistage deep CNN Wang <i>et al.</i> [15]	0.903
Genetic Algorithm Thounaojam <i>et al.</i> [2]	0.89
Average F1 Score in our system	0.926

As the entire study is based on stochastic optimization technique, the exact computation times varies from one run to another, but on an average the computation time depends on the stochastic optimization in the first phase, but in the second phase the time needed is bare minimum.

C. Conclusion and Future Work

In our work, a perceptual Video Shot Boundary Detection algorithm is proposed. To counter the problem of illumination the Local Binary Pattern is used. In the feature extraction part RGB image is converted to equivalent Gray Scale Image. The algorithm proposed in this paper is robust and capable of detecting better accurate transition in terms of accuracy measures like precision and recall. The proposed method has two important steps, first step is detecting the possible abrupt transition from the videos and in the second step prune the extraneous transition frames detected in the first stage. The proposed systems are evaluated under standard databases such as TRECVID 2001 and TRECVID 2007. A comparison report has been prepared, from the comparison report, it is clear that proposed system outperforms the existing shot boundary detection methodologies in case of abrupt transition.

In future we plan to extend our work beyond detecting the hard transitions. We can extend the work to detect the soft transitions like Fade, Dissolve, and Wipe transition which can be a great tool in application for content based video retrieval or other video processing application.

VI. REFERENCES

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